

Renewability Index of energy systems. The case of the global electricity with focus on its infrastructure between 1900 and 2050.

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ABSTRACT

The Renewability Index (RI) of energy systems indicates the amount of net renewable exergy captured from nature for each unit of non-renewable exergy invested in the infrastructure of the technology and their utilization. This RI builds on the concept of exergy cost since it considers the non-renewable exergy sources used in energy production, both direct (fuels) and indirect (infrastructure, measure through exergy cost) use. Indirect use includes the extraction and refining of the materials used in the infrastructure. Therefore, conventional power plants present a RI below zero, since no net renewable exergy is captured and non-renewable exergy is destroyed in the production process. In the case of renewables, the RI would be greater than zero in case it captures more renewable exergy than the non-renewable exergy invested in its infrastructure. Thus, this study applies this concept to the global electricity system between 1900 and 2050, photovoltaics and wind technologies to study the role of its infrastructure. From 2017 onwards, the IEA's Net-Zero Emission (NZE) scenario is used. The results show that, until 2028, the global electrical system is not renewable, as its RI is less than zero. From this point onward, it begins to increase rapidly, reaching 7 MJ/MJ by 2050. On the other hand, wind technology shows an RI of up to 14 MJ/MJ by 2050, while photovoltaic technology reaches 3.4 MJ/MJ by the same year. These results indicate that, despite accounting for a significant penetration of renewable technologies, efforts must be increased to reduce the non-renewable exergy cost of renewable infrastructures. The concept of the RI provides a metric to quantify the actual amount of exergy captured by an energy system and could be extended to assess the degree of renewability of society.

1 INTRODUCTION

Electricity is the essential vector of the energy transition. It is the easiest form of energy to capture from renewable sources using renewable technologies, with the most important being hydropower, wind power, and photovoltaic power. Consequently, electricity generation requires both production means (infrastructure) and energy (fuels). In the case of renewable technologies, the fuels can be considered free, as they correspond to the potential energy of water, the kinetic energy of wind, or the radiant energy of the sun, as in the previous examples. However, the infrastructure is not free, as it depends on a large amount of materials that require significant energy for extraction and production European Commission: Joint Research Centre et al., 2020; International Energy Agency, 2023. This raises an important question: How renewable are renewable technologies and the electrical system?

Answering this question requires appropriate analytical tools. In this regard, exergy is the most suitable thermodynamic property for several reasons. First, it represents the maximum amount of useful work that an energy system can provide, which is precisely the purpose of an energy system: to deliver useful work for productive processes. Second, exergy is not conserved, which indicates the degradation (or quality) of the natural resources used. Third, it allows the integration of energy and matter through the concept of exergy cost. Exergy cost indicates the amount of exergy that has been destroyed to manufacture a product Valero et al., 1986. In this way, exergy cost captures both dimensions of the energy transition: 1) fuels (exergy, direct consumption), and 2) infrastructure (exergy cost, indirect consumption). However, to answer the question posed in this article, a third dimension must be added to distinguish between the origin of the exergy: renewable or non-renewable. This dimension is crucial to understanding the sustainability of the energy transition.

Other authors Granovskii et al., 2007; Stanek et al., 2018; Szargut et al., 2002 have previously worked on the distinction between renewable and non-renewable exergy and its significant implications. Nevertheless, calculating the exergy of electricity and its infrastructure is particularly challenging because electricity itself is used to produce the materials later employed in electricity generation. This creates a feedback loop that must be resolved. Thus, this article builds on previous studies Torrubia et al., 2023, 2024a, 2024b to calculate the renewability of global electricity between 1900 and 2050, as well as photovoltaic and wind technologies. For this purpose, the concept of the Renewability Index (RI) is used, which indicates the amount of renewable exergy captured per unit of non-renewable exergy invested in the infrastructure.

2 DATA AND METHODOLOGY

The methodology of this study is mainly based in two previous papers: 1) “Non-renewable and renewable leveled exergy cost of electricity (LE_{ExCOE}) with focus on its infrastructure: 1900–2050” Torrubia et al., 2024b and 2) “Renewable exergy return on investment (RE_{ExROI}) in energy systems. The case of silicon photovoltaic panels” Torrubia et al., 2024a. The first study calculated the evolution of the exergy cost of electricity disaggregated in non-renewable and renewable sources. The methodology of this study is first explained in Section 2.1. The second paper established the calculation of the renewable exergy return on investment (RE_{ExROI}), i.e., the renewability index (RI) of this paper. The RI used in this paper refers to a more general term which can be also applied to other systems beyond energy systems. For instance, soils and plants which capture renewable energy through the photosynthesis also needs non-renewable resources; and therefore, the term RI is preferable. However, this paper is focused in an energy system: the global electricity between 1900 and 2050. Therefore, RE_{ExROI} and RI are used synonymously in the following.

2.1 Non-renewable and renewable exergy cost of global electricity

The first step in calculating the renewability index (RI) of electricity is to disaggregate the exergy cost according to its origin, distinguishing between non-renewable and renewable sources. However, this calculation is challenging. The main difficulty lies in the fact that the infrastructure for electricity generation requires electricity for its manufacturing. For example, electricity is needed to produce steel or silicon, which are later used in solar panels to generate electricity. This concept is illustrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Calculation scheme of the global exergy cost of electricity, distinguishing between fuel and infrastructure and showing the non-renewable and renewable origins of exergy sources.

Figure 1 also shows that the study Torrubia et al., 2024b considered 34 metals and materials (Ag, Al, Au, B, Cd, Co, Cr, Cu, Dy, Fe, In, Li, Mg, Mn, Mo, Nb, Nd, Ni, Pb, Pr, Si, Sn, Ta, Tb, Ti, Zn, steel (unalloyed, low-alloyed, and stainless), concrete, plastic, glass, and solar glass) that make up the infrastructure of the eight main technologies: coal, oil, and natural gas plants, nuclear plants, hydropower, biomass, wind, and photovoltaic technology. Material intensity, meaning the amount of material required for infrastructure, and other key variables for the calculation, such as the lifespan of the infrastructure or the capacity factor of renewable technologies, were obtained from various sources Ashby, 2013; European Commission: Joint Research Centre et al., 2020; International Energy Agency, 2023; Lallana et al., 2024. Regarding material intensity, it is important to highlight that a constant improvement in photovoltaic panels has been considered, meaning that newer panels require fewer materials. This assumption is crucial because photovoltaic panels show a continuous decrease in their material intensity. For example, silicon and silver intensity has decreased significantly in recent decades. Silicon consumption dropped from 16 t/MW in 2004 to 4 t/MW in 2018, and is expected to fall between 3 and 2 t/MW by 2028, while silver

usage declined from 25 t/GW in 2016 to 5-1 t/GW by 2050 European Commission: Joint Research Centre et al., 2020.

Figure 1 illustrates how the exergy cost of fuels, representing the direct consumption of exergy, is classified into three categories based on their origin:

- **Fossil:** This category includes three components: coal, oil, and natural gas. These are non-renewable, and the exergy of these fuels is directly linked to CO₂ emissions. Thus, through exergy, this category captures the concept of sustainability.
- **Nuclear:** This category refers to nuclear fuel, mainly uranium. It is important to note that extraction and refining processes are not considered, which would increase its exergy cost. This category is also classified as non-renewable.
- **Renewable:** This category includes exergy from renewable sources, namely the potential energy of water, the kinetic energy of wind, solar radiation, and the calorific value of biomass. The first three are considered 100% renewable as nature provides them for free. However, biomass may involve non-renewable inputs, such as fertilizers used in production or fossil fuels used for transportation. These non-renewable inputs are not considered in this study.

On the other hand, the exergy cost of infrastructure is divided into the same categories as the exergy cost of fuels (fossil, nuclear, and renewable). This is because electricity incorporates all three categories and is used in material production, as shown in Figure 1. In addition to electricity, the exergy cost of infrastructure also includes the exergy cost of fossil fuels used in infrastructure. For instance, steel production requires a substantial amount of coal in addition to electricity. Thus, the exergy cost of infrastructure is classified into three categories: 1) fossil fuels, used directly or derived from electricity consumption, 2) nuclear, which only derives from electricity consumption, and 3) renewable, which also only derives from electricity consumption.

In total, there are six categories of exergy cost: 1) fossil fuels as fuels (FF Fuel), 2) fossil fuels embedded in infrastructure (FF Infrs.), 3) nuclear fuels (Nuc Fuel), 4) nuclear fuels embedded in infrastructure (Nuc Infrs.), 5) renewable exergy captured (REN Fuel), and 6) renewable exergy embedded in infrastructure (REN Infrs.).

Once the origin of the exergy cost is clarified, it is essential to describe the transformation of fuels into electricity through infrastructure. A progressive improvement in the efficiency of fossil fuel plants is considered. For example, the efficiency of coal plants was estimated at 20% in 1900, improved to 25% by 1950, reached 30% in 2000, and stabilized at 35% thereafter. Natural gas followed the same efficiency as coal until 1995, as it was primarily used in similar power plants. However, in 2005, with the adoption of combined cycles, its efficiency surged to 45%, and it is assumed to increase to 55% by 2050. Oil-fired plants maintain the same efficiency as coal but with a maximum of 30%. Linear progress between years has been considered. These estimates were obtained from International Energy Agency, 2021, 2023; Torrubia et al., 2024b. Meanwhile, the efficiency of nuclear and renewable plants is assumed to be 100%. In other words, producing 1 MJ of renewable or nuclear electricity requires 1 MJ of renewable or nuclear energy. This is known as the "physical content method" (PCM) and has been chosen because it is the most suitable when analyzing the electrical grid as a whole Sousa et al., 2017.

Another crucial aspect of the methodology is the electricity feedback loop, as shown in Figure 1. Therefore, it is important to trace back to the earliest available historical data. Historical electricity generation data from 1900 to 2017 was gathered from Pinto et al., 2023, and from 2017 onward, the International Energy Agency's (IEA) Net Zero Emissions (NZE) scenario International Energy Agency, 2021 is used until 2050. These two sources cover the entire study period from 1900 to 2050.

In the first year of the study (1900), the exergy cost of electricity in infrastructure is not considered. Thus, the exergy cost of electricity in that year ($ExCOE_{1900}$) is the sum of the exergy cost of fossil-based infrastructure ($B_{I(FF)1900}^*$) and the exergy cost of fuels (B_{F1900}^*), which only includes coal and renewable hydropower, as these were the only technologies in operation at the time. This concept is illustrated in Figure 1, excluding the electricity feedback loop, and is represented by equation 1.

$$ExCOE_{1900} = B_{F1900}^* + B_{I(FF)1900}^* \quad (1)$$

Once the exergy cost of electricity for a given year is known ($ExCOE_{1900}$), it is possible to calculate the exergy cost of electricity for the following year ($ExCOE_{1901}$). However, in this case, it is also necessary to account for

the exergy cost of the infrastructure due to electricity consumption. This is calculated by multiplying the exergy of the electricity required for the infrastructure ($B^{I(EL)1901}$) by the exergy cost of electricity from the previous year ($ExCOE_{1900}$). This new term is added to the exergy cost of the fossil-based infrastructure ($B^{I(FF)1901}$) and the exergy cost of the fuels (B^*F_{1901}). This calculation is represented in Equation 2.

$$ExCOE_{1901} = B_{F_{1901}}^* + B_{I(FF)_{1901}}^* + B_{I(EL)_{1901}}^* \cdot ExCOE_{1900} \quad (2)$$

Once the exergy cost for the year 1901 is calculated, the cost for 1902 can be determined by following the same dynamic procedure. The general calculation of ExCOE for any given year is shown in Equation 3.

$$ExCOE_i = B_{F_i}^* + B_{I(FF)_i}^* + B_{I(EL)_i}^* \cdot ExCOE_{i-1} \quad (3)$$

In this way, it is possible to calculate the exergy cost of electricity (ExCOE), measured in MJ, between 1900 and 2050, disaggregated into six categories derived from three sources: fossil, nuclear, or renewable. These sources are further divided into their direct consumption as fuel or their indirect use as infrastructure.

2.2 Non-renewable and renewable levelized exergy cost of renewable technologies

Calculating the global exergy cost of electricity is challenging due to the feedback loop previously discussed. However, the leveled calculation for renewable technologies is more straightforward. This calculation is represented graphically in Figure 2. The process starts with the exergy cost of electricity (ExCOE), calculated using Equation 3. With this value, along with the exergy cost of photovoltaic exergy ($B_{F_{PV_i}}$), the exergy cost of photovoltaic infrastructure due to fossil fuels ($B_{I(FF)_{PV_i}}$), and the exergy cost of photovoltaic infrastructure due to electricity ($B^{*I(EL)_{PV_i}}$), it is possible to calculate the exergy cost of photovoltaic electricity ($ExCOE_{PV_i}$) for a given year i , using Equation 4. Note that Equation 4 is analogous to Equation 3, but specifically applied to the case of photovoltaics.

Figure 2: Diagram of the exergy cost calculation for photovoltaic electricity, distinguishing between fuel and infrastructure while indicating the non-renewable and renewable origins of the exergy sources.

$$ExCOE_{PV_i} = B_{F_{PV_i}}^* + B_{I(FF)_{PV_i}}^* + B_{I(EL)_{PV_i}}^* \cdot ExCOE_{i-1} \quad (4)$$

Once the exergy cost of photovoltaic electricity ($ExCOE_{PV_i}$) is calculated, the next step is to compute its levelized cost. The levelized exergy cost represents an average exergy cost for a given year, accounting for both the installed capacity in that year and the capacity from previous years. This is calculated in this way because the photovoltaic production in 2025, for example, also relies on photovoltaic panels from earlier years, such as from 2020. The levelized exergy cost for photovoltaic electricity ($LExCOE_{PV_i}$) is calculated using equation 5, where n represents the years since the technology began operation, i is the year of analysis, $\%P_{install-PV_i}$ is the percentage of capacity installed in the analysis year, and $Electricity_{PV_i}$ is the electricity produced by photovoltaics in the analysis year.

$$LExCOE_{PV_i} = \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{ExCOE_{PV_i}}{Electricity_{PV_i}} \cdot \%P_{install-PV_i} \quad (5)$$

$LExCOE_{PV_i}$ has units of MJ/MJ, making it a unitary exergy cost. The same calculation used for the levelized exergy cost of photovoltaic electricity, $LExCOE_{PV_i}$, is applied to wind electricity, $LExCOE_{WIND_i}$. To do this, the *PV* index is replaced by *WIND* in equations 4 and 5. Both $LExCOE_{PV_i}$ and $LExCOE_{WIND_i}$ are analyzed between the years 2020 and 2050, as this is the period in which they play a central role according to the IEA's NZE scenario. It should be noted that both $LExCOE_{PV_i}$ and $LExCOE_{WIND_i}$ are broken down into three sources for infrastructure: fossil, nuclear, or renewable, since their calculation is based on $ExCOE_i$ from equation 3. However, they only consider one fuel type: renewable, as both $LExCOE_{PV_i}$ and $LExCOE_{WIND_i}$ are renewable technologies.

2.3 Renewability index (RI)

The renewability index (RI) indicates the amount of renewable exergy that a power system returns for each unit of non-renewable exergy invested in it. This paper studies three cases: the global electricity system from 1900 to 2050, photovoltaic panels from 2020 to 2050, and wind technology from 2020 to 2050. In Sections 2.1 and 2.2, these three cases are broken down into non-renewable and renewable exergy costs.

For the global electricity system, the term $B_{NR_i}^*$ is calculated, which includes all the non-renewable exergy cost of global electricity, i.e., the sum of the following categories: 1) fossil fuels as fuel (FF Fuel), 2) fossil fuels embedded in infrastructure (FF Infras.), 3) nuclear fuels (Nuc Fuel), and 4) nuclear fuels embedded in infrastructure (Nuc Infras.). Note that the term $B_{NR_i}^*$ also includes fossil and nuclear fuels used as fuel, not just the infrastructure. Based on the term $B_{NR_i}^*$ and $Electricity_i$, which represents the amount of electricity produced in a given year, the RI_i can be calculated through equation 6.

$$RI_{ExCOE_i} = \frac{Electricity_i - B_{NR_i}^*}{B_{NR_i}^*} \quad (6)$$

For photovoltaic technologies, the term $LExCOE_{PV_{NR_i}}$ is calculated, which includes all the non-renewable exergy cost of photovoltaic technology. This is the sum of the following categories: fossil fuels embedded in infrastructure (FF Infras.) and nuclear fuels embedded in infrastructure (Nuc Infras.). In this case, only the infrastructure terms are included because the fuels are always renewable. Therefore, the renewability index of photovoltaics, RI_{PV_i} , serves as an indicator of the renewability of the infrastructure. One advantage of using the renewability index is that infrastructure originating from renewable sources (the category REN Infras.) is also counted as renewable. Since $LExCOE_{PV_{NR_i}}$ is measured in MJ/MJ, the electricity produced in a given year ($Electricity_i$, as shown in equation 6) is equal to 1. Thus, equation 7 shows how to calculate the RI_{PV_i} .

$$RI_{PV_i} = \frac{1 - LExCOE_{PV_{NR_i}}}{LExCOE_{PV_{NR_i}}} \quad (7)$$

The renewability index for wind energy (RI_{WIND_i}) is also calculated using equation 7, but with the subscript *PV* replaced by *WIND*.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section presents, in section 3.1, the results related to section 2.1, in section 3.2 the results related to section 2.2, and in section 3.3 the results related to section 2.3.

3.1 Exergy cost of global electricity (ExCOE)

Figure 3 shows the exergy cost of global electricity between 1900 and 2050. It displays the term $Electricity_i$ with a solid black line, and the exergy cost is represented by bars, broken down into the categories previously discussed: 1) fossil fuels as fuels (FF Fuel, light gray), 2) fossil fuels embedded in infrastructure (FF Infras., dark gray), 3) nuclear fuels (Nuc Fuel, light purple), 4) nuclear fuels embedded in infrastructure (Nuc Infras., dark purple), 5) renewable exergy captured (REN Fuel, light green), and 6) renewable exergy embedded in infrastructure (REN Infras., dark green).

Figure 3 shows how exergy captures three essential aspects for the analysis of the energy transition: fuels, infrastructure, and sustainability (non-renewable or renewable). All of these aspects are analyzed using the same property and units, making them comparable.

Figure 3: Evolution of the exergy cost of electricity (ExCOE) between 1900 and 2050 compared to the electricity production ($Electricity_i$). Torrubbia et al., 2024b.

It can be observed that until 2000, the exergy invested in infrastructures (FF Infr., NUC Infr., and REN Infr.) was relatively low, driven by: (i) lower electricity generation and (ii) the dominance of fossil energy sources, which generally require fewer materials compared to renewable energy infrastructures Slameršak et al., 2022; Valero et al., 2018.

However, since 2010, this trend began to change due to increasing investments in renewable energy. Between 2010 and 2020, non-renewable fuel (fossil and nuclear) only increased by 4% (from 161.6 EJ to 168.2 EJ), but the exergy cost of non-renewable infrastructure tripled (from 1.1 EJ to 3.5 EJ). Between 2020 and 2050, the energy transition accelerates, according to the IEA's NZE scenario, with the exergy cost of non-renewable infrastructures increasing annually by 4.65–8.26 EJ, representing an increase of 133% to 237% compared to 2020. However, at the same time, the fossil fuel exergy cost decreases from 158 EJ in 2020 to 2 EJ in 2050, a 98.8% reduction.

Therefore, the energy transition is characterized by a shift from the direct consumption of fuels to their indirect consumption or investment in infrastructure. However, the indirect consumption of fuels in infrastructure is preferable because the total use of fossil fuels decreases, reducing the consumption of non-renewable resources and increasing renewability. This conclusion is supported by other studies, such as Slameršak et al., 2022.

3.2 Levelized exergy cost of renewable technologies (LExCOE)

Figures 4 and 5 show the levelized exergy cost of photovoltaic ($LExCOE_{PV_i}$) and wind ($LExCOE_{WIND_i}$) electricity between 2000 and 2050, respectively. They display the exergy captured from the sun (represented by a yellow bar, REN Fuel (SunLight)) and the exergy captured from the wind (represented by a green bar, REN Fuel (Wind)). This exergy is always equal to 1 in both cases, as both ($LExCOE_{PV_i}$) and ($LExCOE_{WIND_i}$) are normalized in MJ/MJ. On the other hand, the infrastructure is represented in the same way as in Figure 3: fossil fuels embedded in the infrastructure (FF Infr., dark gray), nuclear fuels embedded in the infrastructure (Nuc Infr., dark purple), and renewable exergy embedded in the infrastructure (REN Infr., dark green).

The exergy cost due to infrastructure follows a similar pattern in both technologies. Initially, the exergy costs from the infrastructure are high: 1.84 MJ/MJ for photovoltaics and 0.20 MJ/MJ for wind, with 95% of these being non-renewable. However, these exergy costs decrease rapidly to 0.26 MJ/MJ for photovoltaics and 0.08 MJ/MJ for wind, with 88% being non-renewable. This rapid decline (86% in photovoltaics and 59% in wind) can be explained by the fact that the installation of infrastructure requires significant exergy investment but does not generate electricity immediately. Therefore, the ($LExCOE$) is high during the years of major installations but gradually decreases over

Figure 4: Evolution of LExCOE_{PV} between 2020 and 2050. Torrubia et al., 2024b.

time due to amortization. The decrease is more pronounced in photovoltaics (86% compared to 59%) because it is assumed that the intensity of silicon and silver gradually decreases due to technological improvements. For instance, silicon consumption dropped from 16 t/MW in 2004 to 4 t/MW in 2018, and it is expected to fall to 3-2 t/MW by 2028, while silver usage decreased from 25 t/GW in 2016 to 5-1 t/GW by 2050 European Commission: Joint Research Centre et al., 2020.

Other studies Koppelaar, 2017; Torrubia et al., 2024a confirm this trend, as the reduction in material use and improvements in performance led to an increase in the average EROI of photovoltaic energy from 2008 onward, reaching an average of 14.4 compared to 7 before 2008 Koppelaar, 2017.

On the other hand, the material intensity of wind technology has been considered constant, as no significant improvements are expected in the coming years.

Another key aspect is the penetration of renewables in infrastructure due to the feedback loop. As the energy transition progresses, electricity will increasingly become renewable, in line with the IEA-NZE projections used in this article. Therefore, the materials used in infrastructure will incorporate more renewable energy through electricity. Due to this effect, renewable exergy embedded in infrastructure in 2020 was around 5%, but by 2050, it will rise to 12%.

3.3 Renewability index (RI)

Figure 6 shows the evolution of the global renewability index for electricity (RI_{ExCOE}) between 1900 and 2050. It is divided into two sections for analysis: the first between 1900 and 2010, which is expanded in Figure 6, and the second between 2010 and 2050, which is expanded in Figure 7.

The period between 1900 and 2010 is characterized by relatively constant RI values, ranging from -0.7 MJ/MJ to -0.5 MJ/MJ. During this period, RI is always negative, meaning that for each MJ of electricity produced, between 0.70 and 0.53 MJ of non-renewable exergy is destroyed. This is significant because non-renewable exergy cannot be replenished in the short term and, therefore, is no longer available for future generations. Hence, these resources can be considered lost forever. This is because, during the 1900-2010 period, most of the generation came from fossil sources, and the deployment of renewables was mostly limited to hydropower.

Figure 3 shows the period between 2010 and 2050. For analysis purposes, it has been subdivided into three periods: 2010-2027, 2027-2041, and 2041-2050, as shown in Figure 7.

The subperiod from 2010 to 2027 marks the beginning of the energy transition. It is important to note that the

Figure 5: Evolution of LExCOE_{WIND} between 2020 and 2050. Torrubia et al., 2024b.

data is historical up until 2017, and from that year onward, the IEA’s NZE scenario begins. Between 2010 and 2020, RI increases from -0.53 MJ/MJ to -0.44 MJ/MJ, which represents a linear increase of 0.0089 MJ/MJ per year. Although this change may seem small, a trend shift from the previous period (1900-2010 in Figure 6) begins to emerge. This is due to the deployment of new renewable technologies, especially wind and photovoltaic power, starting in 2010. However, a more significant change is observed between 2020 and 2027. During this period, RI increases at a rate of 0.0572 MJ/MJ per year, rising from -0.44 MJ/MJ to -0.04 MJ/MJ, although the improvement remains nearly linear. The year 2027 is significant as it marks the last year with a negative RI.

The subperiod between 2027 and 2041 shows a trend shift compared to the previous ones. During this phase, RI increases exponentially at an annual rate of 33%. It rises from just 0.04 MJ/MJ in 2027 to 6.11 MJ/MJ in 2041. This abrupt change in trend is due to the rapid deployment of renewables, especially wind and photovoltaic technologies, according to the IEA’s NZE scenario used in this study. In parallel with the deployment of renewables, fossil technologies such as coal and natural gas are also being dismantled, further boosting the growth of RI.

The subperiod from 2041 to 2050 shows a stabilization in the growth of RI, returning to a linear growth rate from 6.11 MJ/MJ in 2041 to 7.18 MJ/MJ in 2050, increasing at a rate of 0.11 MJ/MJ per year. This slowdown in growth is due to the fact that, in the previous phase (2027-2041), non-renewable technologies were largely phased out, and the deployment of renewable infrastructure was already underway.

By 2050, 91% of electricity will come from renewable sources according to the IEA’s NZE scenario. Therefore, most of the exergy cost of the infrastructures corresponds to these technologies, as the exergy cost of infrastructure for non-renewable technologies is very low compared to that of renewable technologies. Moreover, non-renewable technologies contribute only 9% of the electricity. The exergy cost of the infrastructure in 2050 is 9.69E+12 MJ, of which 7.23E+12 MJ is non-renewable, i.e., 75%, and 2.37E+14 MJ of electricity is produced in that year. Therefore, when calculating RI in 2050 using only non-renewable infrastructure, which belongs almost entirely to renewable technologies, the result is 31.75 MJ/MJ. While the global RI value of 7.18 MJ/MJ refers to the overall energy mix, the 31.75 MJ/MJ value specifically refers to the RI of renewable technologies, as it only considers the infrastructure. Thus, renewable technologies can capture about 32 MJ of renewable exergy for every 1 MJ of non-renewable exergy invested in infrastructure. In other words, to produce 1 MJ of renewable exergy, 0.03 MJ of non-renewable exergy is used to produce the materials for the infrastructure. Therefore, the reliance of renewable technologies on fossil fuels continues, although to a much lesser extent.

After analyzing the RI of the global electrical system between 1900 and 2050, the RI of photovoltaic and wind technologies between 2020 and 2050 is examined, as shown in Figure 8. The RI of wind technology shows positive values throughout the period, from 2021 (4.1 MJ/MJ) to 2050 (14.0 MJ/MJ). These results are due to the low

Figure 6: Renewation Index (RI) of global electricity between 1900-2050 under Net Zero Emissions (NZE) scenario from the International Energy Agency (IEA).

Figure 7: Renewation Index (RI) of global electricity between 2010-2050 under Net Zero Emissions (NZE) scenario from the International Energy Agency (IEA).

non-renewable exergy cost of wind, as shown in Figure 5. The wind RI increases approximately linearly, with an annual increase of 0.348 MJ/MJ.

On the other hand, the RI of photovoltaic technology begins to show positive values starting in 2024, as indicated in the expanded chart in Figure 8. This is significant because, before this point, these technologies did not capture net renewable exergy. In other words, the non-renewable exergy invested during these years was greater than the renewable exergy returned. However, from this point onward, the trend reverses, and these energy systems begin to capture net renewable exergy. By 2050, photovoltaic electricity reaches an RI of 3.4 MJ/MJ. The RI of photovoltaic technology increases linearly at a rate of 0.128 MJ/MJ per year for electricity. Thus, it follows the same linear trend as wind technologies. This increase is primarily due to the amortization of infrastructure, as explained in Figures 4 and 5.

Figure 8 also shows the RI_{ExCOE} , that is, the renewability index of global electricity (from Figures 6 and 7). It can be observed that the RI_{ExCOE} in 2050 lies between RI_{WIND} and RI_{PV} . This result makes sense because, according to the IEA's NZE scenario, a significant portion of the electricity supply in 2050 will come from these technologies.

Finally, the renewability index (RI) can be relatively compared to the EROI calculated by other studies. The EROI,

Figure 8: Renewation Index (RI) of wind, PV, and ExCOE between 2020-2050 under Net Zero Emissions (NZE) scenario from the International Energy Agency (IEA)

energy return on investment, indicates the amount of energy returned for the amount of energy invested in an energy system. However, it has two main issues: 1) it uses energy, so it does not account for the quality of the energy resources used, and 2) it does not distinguish between the use of non-renewable and renewable energy sources. The second point is crucial for sustainability, as the EROI is always positive, even when fossil fuels are used. The economy should minimize the consumption of non-renewable resources because their use depletes them for future generations. The RI index addresses this aspect and penalizes it, allowing for the possibility of RI values below zero, meaning that non-renewable natural resources are being depleted.

The literature shows photovoltaic EROI values between 5.0-14.4 MJ/MJ Ludin et al., 2018, while the RI in this study ranges from -0.4 to 3.4 MJ/MJ. This difference arises because, in this thesis, the RI is calculated from the $LExCOE_{PV,NRI}$, meaning that the non-renewable exergy costs of previous generations of photovoltaic technologies are accounted for in current photovoltaic technologies (see equation 5), which causes the exergy cost reduction to be slower. On the other hand, this has little impact on wind energy, as the material intensity of this technology is considered constant over time, unlike photovoltaic technology, so its results are directly comparable to those in the literature. Thus, the literature places the wind EROI between 5-12 MJ/MJ Dupont et al., 2020; Muteri et al., 2020, while this thesis places it in the range of 4-14 MJ/MJ. Therefore, the results obtained are consistent with the literature.

4 CONCLUSIONS

- Exergy and exergy cost cover all three dimensions of the energy transition: fuels, infrastructure, and sustainability (non-renewable or renewable). This is done using the same property and units, making the comparison valid.
- The energy transition shifts non-renewable fuel consumption to infrastructure. However, this is preferable because renewable infrastructure can capture renewable exergy. Thus, between 2020 and 2050, the energy transition accelerates according to the IEA's NZE scenario, leading to an increase in the non-renewable exergy cost of infrastructure, which rises by 4.65-8.26 EJ annually, or between 133% and 237% compared to 2020. However, at the same time, the fossil exergy cost of fuel decreases from 158 EJ in 2020 to 2 EJ in 2050, a reduction of 98.8%.
- The non-renewable exergy cost of renewable technologies is expected to decrease between 2020 and 2050 due to: 1) the amortization of infrastructure, 2) a reduction in material intensity, especially for photovoltaics, and 3) the use of renewable exergy in infrastructure manufacturing (a feedback process). Thus, the exergy cost decreases from 1.84 MJ/MJ (photovoltaics) and 0.20 MJ/MJ (wind), with 95% of the cost being non-renewable in 2020, to 0.26 MJ/MJ (photovoltaics) and 0.08 MJ/MJ (wind), with 88% of the cost being non-renewable in 2050. Therefore, there is a decrease of 86% for photovoltaics and 59% for wind between 2020 and 2050.
- The renewability of an energy system is measured by the renewal index (RI), which indicates the amount of net renewable exergy captured per unit of non-renewable exergy invested. When the RI is negative, no

renewable exergy is captured, and the system cannot be considered renewable. This occurs in all non-renewable technologies, and also in renewable ones when more non-renewable exergy is invested in infrastructure than the renewable exergy captured.

- The RI is applied to three cases: 1) global electricity from 1900 to 2050, 2) photovoltaic technology, and 3) wind technology.
 1. The RI is negative between 1900 and 2010, with values ranging from -0.7 to -0.5 MJ/MJ. From 2010 onward, it starts increasing, reaching -0.44 MJ/MJ in 2020. Between 2020 and 2027, the increase gains momentum, with an annual increment of 0.0572 MJ/MJ, turning positive in 2028. In other words, from this year onward, the global electricity system becomes renewable according to the NZE scenario of the IEA used in this study. Between 2027 and 2041, the RI growth rate becomes exponential, with an annual increase of 33%, from 0.04 MJ/MJ to 6.11 MJ/MJ. In the final stage studied (2041-2050), the RI growth slows because the majority of the non-renewable technologies are dismantled during the previous stage (2027-2041), reaching 7.18 MJ/MJ in 2050.
 2. The RI for photovoltaics is not positive until 2024. Until this year, the non-renewable exergy invested during these years was greater than the renewable exergy returned. However, the RI increases linearly, at a rate of 0.128 MJ/MJ per year for electricity, reaching 3.4 MJ/MJ in 2050.
 3. The RI for wind is positive throughout the entire study period. In 2020, it is 4.1 MJ/MJ and grows linearly to 14.0 MJ/MJ by 2050.
- The RI analysis of these three cases shows that, despite considering a strong penetration of renewable technologies, efforts should be increased to reduce the non-renewable exergy cost of renewable infrastructures. For example, this could be achieved by extending their lifespan, using recycled materials, or reducing the use of fossil fuels in their manufacturing.
- The RI is preferred over the EROI because: 1) it accounts for the quality of energy through exergy, and 2) it differentiates between non-renewable and renewable energy. This distinction is crucial for analyzing the sustainability of energy systems since the RI penalizes the use of non-renewable exergy, potentially giving values below zero. This indicates that non-renewable resources are being depleted, questioning the sustainability of the process in the long term.
- The RI can be applied to any system to indicate its level of renewability. Its message is powerful because it can be extrapolated to society as a whole. Societies have always needed energy, so this index can show how far our society is from being fully renewable. A value close to zero or negative indicates a society that is depleting the planet's non-renewable resources and will eventually run out. On the other hand, a society with high RI values could sustain itself in the long term.

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